

DEVELOPING SUPPLEMENTARY ENGLISH SPEAKING MATERIALS FOR NURSING VOCATIONAL SCHOOLⁱ

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Abstract:

The objectives of this study are: (1) to develop appropriate supplementary English speaking materials for students in learning speaking skill in Tenth Grade in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan. (2) To see the students' perception toward this supplementary English speaking materials in nursing vocational. The type of this study is Research and Development (R&D) by Borg and Gall (1983). The subjects of the research were X grade student. This study involved 30 grade ten students of nursing vocational. The instruments of the study were observation, interview, questionnaires and document analysis. The results of the needs analysis questionnaire were analyzed by using percentage. To validate the appropriateness of the book, the developed materials book was reviewed and evaluated by the expert. The result of needs analysis showed that in the part of students' responded background it was found that the students have a lack experience about learning speaking English especially in nursing vocational. In the target needs and learning needs showed that the students needed materials for speaking which were attractive and interesting and based on nursing vocational. The product of this study was supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational. This product consisted of three units. Each unit had 10 activities and five stages related to curriculum 2013. Those five stages were observing, questioning, gathering information, associating, and communicating. The result of the book evaluation from the expert showed that the developed supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational school were categorized as strongly agreed. Moreover, the result of students' perception about this product showed that the

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students mostly agree that the book suitable to be applied in the teaching and learning process especially in speaking. Thus, it can be concluded that supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational had been appropriated for X grade students in nursing vocational school.

Keywords: supplementary, English speaking materials, nursing vocational, curriculum 2013

1. Introduction

In this globalization era, there will be more and more developments which will occur in this country. The use of international languages such as English is prevalent, as well as in the world of health which includes the world of nursing. Moreover, English language education is beneficial regarding finding the source of knowledge about nursing science which mostly comes from international journals. Besides, if a person can speak English, it will be an additional value for the prospective hospital worker, because most of medical equipment and medicines come from abroad. English is essential for the nurse because the patient comes from different culture, shapes and speaks in different language. This is very useful for the vocational nursing students because they still have plenty of time to learn and master English as their basic skill before entering Medical University.

Based on peremenkes number 1534/menkes/sk/x/2005 about curriculum of nursing vocational education, curriculum materials are divided into three components, namely the normative, adaptive and productive components. The normative part directed to the formation of character and attitude. An adaptive element provided to develop the concept of creative and logical thinking that support the ability of graduates to adapt their self in the development of science and technology. The productive component is given to equip skills and attitude at work based on capabilities demanded by the world of work. Moreover, in the adaptive element, English materials aims to cultivate the ability to communicate in order to anticipate the era of globalization and increasing rapid flow of the information. It means that English speaking materials are important to be developed to fulfilling the nursing students' needs.

Additionally, in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan, speaking English is somewhat tricky for senior high school students primarily in the tenth-grade for nursing vocational. Based on observation and interview with the English teacher and the students in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan, it is revealed that most of the students had low ability in speaking English in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan. This is because of several reasons. First, the researcher found that the students made many mistakes in speaking English like grammatical mistakes and poor vocabularies. Second, the students have a lack of motivation in speaking because the teacher just taught them through asking questions. It means that the student needs materials that can support and enhance their speaking in English. Third, there are two kinds of text book the teacher used in a teacher, module and "Get along with English" by Erlangga. The book

(module) for English subject is expensive, and the students cannot buy it. Also, the content of the book "Get along with English" not specific to fulfill the student's vocational needs and some of the materials are not relevance with the syllabus.

Therefore, to overcome the problems above based on the condition of the textbook, the researcher thought about to make an English speaking materials product as supplementary materials focus on nursing vocational. This research should be developed to help nursing students enhance their ability in English particularly in speaking based on their vocational. Moreover, the vocational school should provide materials based on English for specific purposes related to nursing vocational. Richards (2001 as cited in Gass 2012) says that "...the ESP approach to language teaching is a response to a number of practical concerns: for instance, the need to prepare materials to teach students who have already mastered general English but now need English for use in employment, in this situation, non-English background nurses".

In addition, there are some related studies about supplementary materials development. The first study was conducted by Laela Febriatun, (2016) "Developing English Speaking Materials for Xth Grade of Hotel Accommodation Department in SMK PI Ambarukmo 1 Sleman". She found that the students needed English for their future job. The students like to have speaking activities in class. Moreover, the type of her study is Research and Development (R and D) by Borg and Gall (1983). She used the research procedure that was adapted from Masuhara's model (in Tomlinson, 1998: 247). Then she modified the models into five; conducting need analysis, writing the course grid, designing material or writing the first draft, getting the expert judgment, revising and writing the final draft.

The differences between the previous study with this research are this research used theory of research and development adapted from Borg and Gall (1983), from ten steps the researcher only take six steps. The six steps consist of research and information collecting, planning, develops a preliminary form of product, preliminary field testing, main product revision, and main field testing. Moreover, in collecting the data to takes students' needs analysis, the researcher use theory from Lamb (1996 in Wello and Doliah, 2008), Hutchinson and Water (2004) and Nunan (2004). Moreover, their finding and theories can help and guide the researcher in understanding to develop supplementary materials based on the objective of this research.

1.1 Research Question

How is the development of supplementary materials for speaking skill in nursing vocational in Tenth Grade in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan?

1.2 Objective of Research

To develop appropriate materials for students in learning speaking skill in Tenth Grade in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan.

1.3 Scope and Delimitation

This study deals with developing supplementary English speaking materials, based on nursing vocational students' needs for the first semester of 6th grade student of SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan. Furthermore, the competencies in the syllabus that the researcher will develop are based on students' needs in speaking English materials. Speaking materials in the syllabus 2013 curriculum are hoped students to communicate English effectively. The researcher found that basic competences in students' book in every unit had less speaking activity. Then, the competencies that the researcher will develop are talking about self, complimenting and showing care, expressing an intention, and congratulating others. The researcher just develop 3 unit because in their workplace in the hospital when they are in grade XI as a nurse assistant. The topics related to the main point of what are they going to do in the hospital, greetings, congratulating and complimenting, and caring for the patient. Also, in the book that the used in that school less of speaking activities.

2. Significance of Research

2.1 Theoretical Significance

Theoretically, the researcher expects that the result of this research can be a reference for another researcher who wants to learn more about it. This research can help the students to understand more about the theory of English for specific purposes (ESP).

2.2 Practical Significance

The researcher expects that the result of this research will be useful for:

1. English teacher: the researcher expects that this result of the research would inspire teachers to be more creative in facilitating students with learning materials that are suitable to the students' vocational, based on student needs.
2. Students of SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan, Nursing vocational: the result of the research is expected to help the students in learning English and improve their speaking ability based on their needs and learning objective.
3. Materials developers: the result of the designed materials can be used as a resource and reference for the development of English speaking materials. The materials produced in this research can be combined with other English skills as needed.

2.3 Theoretical Basis

2.3.1 Speaking

The way people talks to each other, to communicate, to deliver what they want to say through speaking. Without speak to people around of us, it is difficult for us to deliver our idea.

2.3.2 Definition of Speaking

Speaking is a process to deliver what people want to say through a language. According to McDonough, Shaw, and Masuhara (2013), *"speaking is not the oral production of written language, but involves learners in the mastery of a wide range of sub-skills, which, added together, constitute an overall competence in the spoken language."* Speaking means to communicate with other people and it can be done in monologues or dialogues. The role of speaking in human life is so important because a human cannot normally live without communicating with other people. Nunan (1991:39) states that *"the successful in speaking is measured through someone able to carry out a conversation in the language."* When someone speaks to another person, there will be a relationship. The relationship itself is communication. In addition, Richard (2002, p.201) also states that *"speaking is used for many different purposes, and each purpose involves different skills"*. It means that we speak based on the situation or the context that we are talking about.

Based on the definition about speaking above, it could be concluded that speaking is the way people talk to others to deliver their opinion and idea, by sounds and words. Furthermore, unlike reading and writing, speaking happened in real time. Usually, people that we are talking to are waiting for you to speak. When we speak, we cannot edit or revise what we want to say, as we can do when we are doing writing.

2.3.3 Teaching Speaking

Teaching speaking is not an easy job. Most of the English teachers often ignore speaking on their teaching and learning process since it is difficult to perform. Some say that it is difficult to assess student's performances. Therefore, when they are teaching in the class, they use Indonesia language. The teacher speaks in English just a little bit because of the reason that the students do not know what they say or explain about the topic in front of the class. Moreover, Bailey (2005) in Songsiri, (2007), state *"Confidence and competence in speaking could be developed from an appropriate syllabus design, methods of teaching, and adequate tasks and materials."* To speak successfully, the students should fulfill some characteristics of a successful speaking activity which can be used to assess the teaching and learning process.

2.3.4 Supplementary Materials

According to McGrath (2002, p. 80) as cited in Udam (2005), *"...supplementary materials refer to materials taken to another source or any other material that is designed for learning purposes."* It means adding something new to provide additional materials in order to supplement the textbooks. Supplementary materials are designed when teachers find that there are no suitable or relevant materials that can be found in the published textbooks. Supplementary materials are designed to help them understand better. In addition, Brown (1994) says that *"...teachers need to supplement materials to promote motivation, which is one of the key factors in learning."* In other words, teachers also need supplementary materials to teach the student to give more input to them and to motivate the learner to get the better understanding.

2.3.5 English for Specific Purposes (ESP)

Robinson (1980) states that "in ESP learner's need are often described regarding performance that is in terms of what the learner will be able to do with the language at the end of a course of study. Whereas in general English course the goal is usually an overall mastery of the language that can be tested on a global language test, the goal of an ESP course is to prepare the learners to carry out a specific task or set of tasks". Furthermore, Richard and Schmidt (2002), also state that "*ESP is a role of English in a language course or program of instruction which the content and aims of the course are fixed by specific needs of a particular group of learners*". It means that ESP has a result to make the learners have a purpose and will be able to develop their capability that suitable with their major.

2.4 Need Analysis

Need analysis in language teaching plays a vital role in the process of designing and carrying out any language course. This research will identify the students' needs for speaking skill in nursing vocational; therefore, the researcher needs some theories about need analysis.

Additionally, regarding learning need, Hutchinson and Water (2004, p 60-62), state that "*the whole ESP process is concerned not with knowing or doing, but with learning.*" It means that learning need is an interesting part to consider how far the activity reflects the target situation needs and how far the needs of the learning situation. Currently, to analyze learning needs, there are some frameworks in analyzing learning needs, that framework can answer the questions that related to the learning needs analysis. It consists of why the students want to take the lesson, how they learn about the language, what resources are available, who are the students, where the subject will take place, and when the subject will take place. It means that learning needs are to find out about the students' condition that related to their minds include their knowledge, skills, and strategies.

Furthermore, learning needs also include input, procedures, setting, learners' role and the teachers' role. Those are known as tasks component in Nunan (2004, p. 40). Nunan (2004, p. 47-70) defines that "*'Input' refers to the learners work on the subject in completing the task based on spoken, written and visual data. Data can be provided by a teacher, a textbook or some other sources. 'Procedures' refers to steps that a learner has to do with the input in the learning task. 'Settings' refers to the classroom arrangements specified or implied in the task. 'Role' refers to the part that teachers and learners are hoped to play in bringing out the learning tasks in the social and interpersonal relationships between the participants*". Thus, it means that learning need gather what the learners' needs in achieving the effectiveness of teaching and learning process based on the student needs analysis. Based on explanations above about needs analysis, it shows that the theory will be beneficial for a researcher to enhance the students' needs. Students' need analysis will be the main data in this research.

3. Methodology of Research

3.1 Research Design

The research design used in this research is research and development (R&D). It focuses on developing supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational in understanding the students' needs in speaking skill.

This research uses the theory from Borg and Gall (1983, p. 772) which defines R&D as a process that can be used to develop and validate the educational product, such as teaching method. Borg and Gall introduced ten steps of conducting Research and development, those are; 1) Research and Information Collecting, 2) Planning, 3) Develop Preliminary Form of Product, 4) Preliminary Field Testing, 5) Main Product Revision, 6) Main Field Testing, 7) Operational Product Revision, 8) Operational Product Field Testing, 9) Final Product Revision and 10) Dissemination/Implementation. Furthermore, Sugiyono (2014, p. 407) states that *"research method to produce a certain product and to examine the effectivity of a product"*. This research is appropriate with the theories above. This is because the researcher will make some product of research that is developing supplementary materials for speaking skill. Here the illustration that the researcher made in applied research and development:

Source: Borg and Gall (1983)

Based on the diagram above, the following is the explanation of research and development that use by the researcher:

- Research and Information Collecting (need analysis): in this first step, would identify students' needs through observation, interview, questionnaire, and document analysis to the students itself. In addition, the researcher uses the textbooks as the document analysis, then identify student needs and teacher perception, because the purpose of the needs analysis is to gather the information about students' needs.

- **Planning:** after identifying students' needs, then the researcher design the materials based on the students' needs analysis. In designing materials, the textbooks focus on the English speaking materials topics that will be developed. Therefore, the researcher considers the core competence and basic competences which underline in English teaching at the vocational senior high school. There are several competencies in the syllabus. The researcher focused on the competencies in the textbooks that will the researcher develop are based on the student's needs analysis. Those competencies are talking about self, congratulating and complimenting others, and expressing an intention. The syllabus consists of core competence, basic competence, topics, unit titles, indicators, input texts, language focus (vocabulary and grammar) and learning procedure/activities.
- **Develop Preliminary Form of Product (re-design):** After planning to develop supplementary materials by looking at textbooks based on the students' needs in speaking English materials, the researcher re-designs it by paying attention to students' needs, data in detail can be useful in the next step that is preliminary field testing.
- **Preliminary Field Testing:** In this step, the researcher will apply the supplementary English speaking materials that already developed by the researcher based on the students' needs analysis.
- **Main Product Revision:** This step about expert validation and includes two experts' verification, which is one English teacher and English lecturer who already know and have many experiences and competencies about research and development.
- **Main Field Testing:** In the last step, based on the supplementary materials for speaking skill, the researcher will apply it in the tenth-grade nursing vocational. Thus, this is the final step in conducting this research and the step also to provide students' response validation sheet.

3.2 Research Setting

3.2.1 Site

The site of this research is SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan, District of Gorontalo sub-district of Bone Bolango. It is located in Deki Street, Huntu Barat village, Bulango Selatan. The vocational in this site is nursing vocational. This research will be conducted in tenth grade in 2017/2018 academic year. The site is selected based on the purpose of the research which identifies students' needs in learning speaking skill in tenth grade.

3.2.2 Participants

The participants of this research are students of SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan who are in tenth grade as new students in the first semester in the academic year of 2017/2018. There are two classes in the tenth grade, but the researcher just taking one class and in this class, which consist of 30 students in nursing vocational.

3.2.3 The technique of Data Collection

In this step, the researcher used theory from Creswell (2008, p. 220) as the instrument of this research. Techniques for collecting the information were observations, interviews, questionnaires and document analysis.

3.2.3.1 Observation

This research uses observation to observe the English teaching-learning process in tenth-grade students of SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan and the textbook that the teacher used to teach English. Furthermore, the indicators are the tenth-grade students and the English teacher.

3.2.3.2 Interview

In this step, the researcher interviews the English teacher about the materials of English for tenth-grade students and what are the students' difficulties in speaking activities. The interview was conducted in SMK Negeri 1 Bulango Selatan in nursing vocational classes. It includes the open-ended questions related to the research, and the researcher records the process of interview.

3.2.3.3 Questionnaire

In this step, the data will be collected through questionnaires. Need analysis that the researcher in applied the questionnaire is proposed by Lamb (1996, p 34-8) in Wello and Doliah (2008, p.79), Hutchinson and Waters (1987) and Nunan (2004).Lamb model of the questionnaire is explored students' background; include name, age, experience in learning English, duration of use English in every day, and the students' proficiency level in English. Moreover, Hutchinson Water explored the target needs include, goals, necessities, lacks and wants. Then, Nunan in explored the learning needs include input, procedures, setting, teachers' role and learners' role. Thus, some part of the questionnaires is transform based on nursing vocational. Here are the organization of questionnaire adapted from Lamb (1996), Hutchinson and Waters (1987) and Nunan (2004).

Table 1: The kind of questionnaires for students nursing vocational school

No.	Aspect	The purpose of the question	References	
1	Responded Background	To find out general learner needs survey	Lamb (1996)	
2	Target Needs	Goal	To find out the reason of learning English	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
3		Necessities	To find out the type of based on target situation.	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
4		Lacks	To find out the gap between learners' proficiency and the demand of the target situation.	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
5		Wants	To find out the learners' want of learning English.	Hutchinson and Waters (1987)
6	Input	To find out appropriate input for English learning materials that students want	Nunan (2004)	

			the most	
7	Learning Needs	Procedures	To find out the suitable procedures that students want the most	Nunan (2004)
8		Setting	To find out the class management of doing the tasks that the students want (individually, in pairs, or in groups)	Nunan (2004)
9		Learners' role	To find out the role of the learner in the learning process	Nunan (2004)
10		Teachers' role	To find out the role of the teacher in doing the tasks	Nunan (2004)

3.2.3.4 Document Analysis

In this step, the researcher will use documents such as textbook, syllabus, lesson plan as a bank data to developing English speaking materials. Based on the textbook that the researcher observed, it was found that there are 3 units of English students' book less of speaking activity in each unit. Furthermore, to analyze the supplementary materials the researcher will use the validation sheet. Finally, the validation sheet which is appropriate to the experts or the advisors is to assess part of the additional English speaking materials that the researcher will develop.

3.2.4 The Technique of Analyzing the Data

There are several steps in analyzing the data based on Creswell theory (2008, pp. 185-192) that will be explained in the diagram below;

Source: Creswell (2008)

A. Step 1 (organized and prepared data)

In this step, the researcher organizes and prepares the data for the analysis step. Furthermore, after researcher conducting the observation, interview, questionnaires to

get students' needs and to plan to develop supplementary materials for speaking skill, the researcher make a list and note based on the result of scanned the data from students' needs in interview and questionnaire.

B. Step 2 (read all the data)

In this step, the researcher will learn all the data based on the data that the researcher found in interview and questionnaire. After that, the researcher will analyze the materials which appropriate to the students' needs in speaking skill.

C. Step 3 (coding process)

In this step, the researcher begins to code the data. Cresswell, (2008, p. 251) states that *"coding is the process of segmenting and labeling text to form descriptions and broad themes in the data."* The researcher will code the data based on the students' need analysis and categorize the data from the participants based on the students' needs. Then, the researcher classifying the data by reading all the transcription and finding the main point of the data which important or not based on all of the topics. After that, the researcher makes columns in each topic that can be as a main topic, arrange every topic into categories.

D. Step 4 (describe in detail)

In this step, the research will describe in detail the information that the researcher get from interview, questionnaires and the document analysis.

E. Step 5 (narrative approach)

In this step, the researcher will use the narrative approach to explaining every data that the researcher find in the process of research.

F. Step 6 (interpreting data)

This is the final step of the research, the researcher will interpreting the data. Thus, the researcher will explain the final result of the supplementary materials for speaking skill based on the steps above and supported by some theory that appropriate with the research questions.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1 Responded Background

Responded background refers to see the student's condition and experience in learning English. The result of the responded background shows that they have a lack of experience in English such as all of them never learn English in English course. Besides, the students use English in the classroom with their friend and the teacher only when the English lesson time. Then, some of the students not always used English with their friend on the outside of the class and not often to practice.

Furthermore, some of them used English in the social media only when they want to updated or posted photos then make a caption on that or what they think but not always. In fact, in the options of the student's proficiency level of English (very good, good, average, and bad), almost all of the students confess that their proficiency level of English is average, while others choose wrongly. By looking at that situation, the researcher considers it is imperative to enhance and give them motivation in learning English especially in speaking English.

4.2 Need Analysis

The model of the questionnaire in this research divided into responded background, target needs and learning needs.

Table 2: The result of need analysis questionnaire

Need Analysis	Task Component	Questions by Item	Categories of Response	Percentage
Target Need	Goals	The goal of learning English	to get a good grade/ pass the examination	(24) 80%
	Necessities	Your English competencies in Speaking	using English but unable to respond	(25) 83,33%
	Lacks	Your difficulties in English speaking ability	Difficulties in discussing either in groups or in pairs	(18)60%
	Wants	After learning English speaking skill, I can...	Communicate with grammar correctly	(21)70%
Learning Need	Setting	The type of class management the students want in doing the task	Learn in pairs	(22) 73,33%
	Input	The length of the text in speaking material	50-150 words	(19) 63,33%
	Input	Input in speaking that students' want	Monologue and dialogue accompanied by list of vocabulary and pronunciation	(20) 66,67%
	Procedures	The type of activity in vocabulary	Matches words with images	(15) 50%
	Procedures	The type of activity in grammar	complete the utterance/dialogue by using the correct grammar	(21) 70%
	Procedures	The type of activity in learning to speak	Discussion	(19) 63,33%
	Procedures	The type of activity of pronunciation the students' want	Repeat the teacher's words that are considered difficult	(25) 83,33%
	Learner's Role	Learner's role in the learning process	Listen to the teacher's explanation well	(20) 66,66%
	Teacher's Role	Teacher's role in the learning process	Providing examples of assignments given to students	(21) 70%

4.3 The Process of English Speaking Materials Development

In the process of English speaking materials development, the researcher did several steps. The content of the questionnaire was given to the students were referred to Lamb, Hutchinson and Water's and Nunan's theory. The items of the questionnaire can be divided into three main parts (responded background, target needs, and learning needs). Thus, the description of all units will be described as below:

4.4 The Description of Unit 1

The title in Unit 1 is "I am a nurse." This is related to talking about self but more focus on the vocational nursing materials. The researcher used the word of "unit" because the researcher focused on references to Jack Richard's book. The title showed the expression of introduction self in this unit. Moreover, the researcher provides "snapshot" as the beginning of the teaching and learning process. The researcher used the word snapshot than warm up because based on the Jack Richard's book. As the word snapshot, the researcher use picture with the purpose to motivate the students' critical thinking in learning speaking English. Below the pictures in the snapshot, the researcher provides some questions that have a purpose to check are they familiar with the pictures or not. The function of the snapshot is to get the students' feedback and snapshot lets the researcher regularly gauge student progress so the researcher can quickly and easily personalize learning and close learning gaps.

In addition, there are fourth tasks provide in parts of unit 1. The task for activity 1 is about pair works. The students are asks to interview their partner related to introduction self. After their interview with the partner that they do not know well, the students will introduce their partner in front of the class. The reason of giving this task, because based on their needs. They wanted to learn in pair. Also, in activity for task 2 is about role play. The students are ask to divide into a groups, each group introduce their self to the partner. Then, they practice in front of the class related with the task their own creativity. This activity related with students' needs, they wanted learn in group and the researcher used role play. Furthermore, in the activity for task 3 is about monologue. The students are asks to introduce their self in front of the class based on the example in the textbook. Also, they are allows to more creative in front of the class. This monologue section included in reading aloud because they make a note about their self and presented it in front of the class. Thus, in the activity for task 4 is about discussion. In this activity, the students will discuss with their group about the questions in the task after that they will discuss it with the other group. The reason of giving this task is based on the students' needs.

Further, language focus consists of vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation. In vocabulary, the students will complete the table by looking at the picture beside the box and explain in front of the class based on their own opinion. In grammar, the students will complete the utterance based on the correct pronoun and practice it with a partner. In pronunciation, the students will repeat the words that the teacher said. Then make a short dialogue based on the example and practice with a partner.

Moreover, in the wrap up the students are asked to choose one topic from three topics are provided. After that, they present it in front of the class. This is suitable to see are they know how to make good communication with others. The last is reflection. The purpose of this section is to facilitate the students with self-assessment activity. Reflection in this unit has a purpose to reveal their insights, understandings, and applications of their learning. Here, the students are asks to answer the several questions about how far they understand about the topic.

4.3 The Description of Unit 2

The title in Unit 2 is "Congratulating and Complimenting Patient." It was related with congratulating and complimenting other in 2013 curriculum student book but focus on the nursing vocational. The title of this unit was taken from the expression that the researcher used. Some expressions used in the nursing environment when they speak to their patient, such as congratulate and compliment the patient. Because nursing jobs require not only treating the patients, who are sick or injured but also offering advice and emotional support to patients and their families. At the beginning of unit 2 provide "snapshot" to scrape their knowledge about treating the patient. The researcher put some pictures which are related to the topic and ask them some questions related to the pictures. Also, the expression of congratulation and complimenting and the suitable respond. Not forget to put the example of the dialogue about those expressions. The researcher asks the students to identify the correct expressions related to the topic.

There were 4 activities in this unit. The activity 1 was started with role-play, the students are asks to read first the dialogue and choose their partner to present in front of the classroom. After that, the students have to classify which one included in the expression of congratulating and complimenting the patient. Activity 2 is about completing the missing dialogue with the correct expression by looking at the picture and present in front of the classroom. Therefore, through this activity, the students not only practice their speaking skill but also they could increase their understanding of nursing talk to the patient related to the topic.

Activity 3 required the students to more critical thinking by asking them to make a dialogue related to the situation and expressions are provided. They can choose which one the situation the like mostly and present in front of the classroom. The goal of giving this activity to the students is to facilitate them identify the appropriate expression and grammar function. Then, in activity 4 is about discussion, in this part the students have to answer several questions related to the topic. The goal of giving this activity is to find out how far their knowledge about congratulating and complimenting related with their self-experienced in their daily life.

Further, in the language focus section, in the part of the vocabulary, the researcher provided some picture related to the students need. They are asks to match the pictures with the correct expression and respond and present it in front of the classroom. The goal of giving this task to make they can classify which one is the best appropriate expression and the respond of that and which one is not. Moreover, in the part of grammar, the students are asks to complete the utterance based on the grammar

of the topic. The researcher used simple past tense, present perfect tense, and present perfect continuous tense. The function is to guide the students more focus on the grammar in use.

In the part of pronunciation, the students are asks to repeat the pronunciation. After that, make a short dialogue and practice in front of the class. The goal is to make them more confident when they speak English related to the topic. After that, in the section of wrap up the students are asked to make simple expression card related to the topic in this unit and present in front of the class room with the partner. By giving this activity, the students will have the summary of anything they have learned in unit 2. Also, the students can be more motivated and creative. Last, in reflection section, there will be some questions that they have to answer to find out the students' achievement about the materials in this unit.

4.4 The Description of Unit 3

The title in this unit is "patient care". The researcher used this title because this was related with the expression of intention and the language feature about would be and be going to. That is why the researcher used the title of patient care in this unit. Through this material, the students could learn more about the kinds of disease that the patient had in the hospital or the clinic. Also, they can learn about the expression that the can use when they face with the patient. Firstly, in the snapshot part, the students are asks to answer several questions based on the pictures are provided. The researcher put one picture of the child who is sick, and then students can identify what kind of disease that the child gets. The aim of giving several pictures was to measure how far the students' knowledge about the type of disease and are they can classify the kind of the disease or not. The researcher applies types of disease which is include the disease based on their level, not the difficult one, related to the situation of the people who are sick in Gorontalo.

Additionally, the students are asks to learn and understand about the expression of intention and the example are provided. Then, in activity 1 was about role-play, the students are asks to learn and read the dialogue which provided and then practice in front of the classroom. When the already practice in front of the class they are ask to answer several questions are provided. The goal of giving this activity is to make them habitual to speak English related to the nursing field. Furthermore, in activity 2 the students have to works in the group. In this activity, there are some box and the example of the conversation below the box. They will ask to choose one or two kinds of disease from the box. After that, they have to walk around the classroom and find one or two friends and ask some questions related to the example. This activity has a goal to make them can be confident to speak with others and encourage their knowledge about treating the patient well.

After that, in the activity 3, the students are asks to make two dialogue based on the situation. The aim of giving this activity is to make them creative to communicate with others. In activity 4 was about discussion, the students are asks to answer several questions related to the situation that already provided in this unit. Then, present in

front of the class about the information that already the students' discuss. Moreover, in the section of language focus, in vocabulary, the students are asks to match the picture with the correct expression and practice with their friend. In grammar, they are asks to complete the utterance in the conversation which already provided with the correct grammar. Then, in the part of pronunciation, the students are asks to listen how to say some words that related to the topic and repeat after the teacher. After that, the students are asked to make a short dialogue and practice it in front of the class with their partner.

Additionally, in the section of wrap up, the students talk about their plan in the future by using the correct text structure will and be going to. Last section was about reflection, the aim is to measure how deep they understand the unit by answer the questions are provided. In conclusion, the main reasons of giving those activities to the students are to measure their comprehension about the English speaking material related to their major. The activity was given to them related to the material of learning. Moreover, in giving the activities to the students based on their needs, where they wanted to work in pairs, groups, discussion, monologue or dialogue, complete the utterance, role play, and match words with pictures.

4.5 The Expert Judgement

After the material was developed, the next step was asking an expert to evaluate the first draft of the materials. This step was called expert judgment in which the experts gave the comment, suggestion and evaluation for the materials whether they already appropriate enough or not. Moreover, the questionnaire is the instrument of expert judgment. The items of the questionnaire were adapted from the standards of materials proposed by *BNSP*. It contains four aspects: content, language, presentation, and layout. The purpose of the questionnaire as the instrument was to find out how far the materials have accomplished those standards. Also, in this part, the experts are filled out the questionnaire about the appropriateness of developing English speaking materials for Nursing vocational school, reasonable language, and the benefit of using English speaking materials for Nursing Vocational School.

4.6 Discussion of Developing Supplementary English Speaking Materials for Nursing Vocational School

In developing supplementary English speaking materials, the researcher used theory from Borg and Gall (1983). There is ten steps theory of Borg and Gall about research and development; research and information collecting, planning, develop a preliminary form of product, preliminary field testing, main product revision, main field testing, operational product revision, operational product field testing, final product revision and dissemination/implementation. From those ten steps, not all of the frameworks that used in developing supplementary English Speaking materials for nursing vocational. The researcher limited her research until main field testing (6 steps) because of the limitation of time and money. Thus, in the seven until ten steps it is used in the big scale o research, while the researcher's product only used on the small scale.

Moreover, before the researcher develops the English speaking materials for nursing vocational, the researcher starts with the first step (research and information collecting). In the part of the research and information collecting, the researcher did observation, interview, using questionnaire, and document analysis. Observation includes the English teaching and learning process in the classroom, curriculum and the textbook the teacher used in teaching English speaking especially in nursing vocational. Based on the finding, in the first observation and interview, they still used the curriculum of KTSP for X grade, XI grade, and XII grade of the students in 2017/2018 academic years. But in the next semester, they will use 2013 curriculum for X grade. So, the book of supplementary English Speaking materials for nursing vocational as the preparation for X grade students in the next semester based on the 2013 curriculum. There are three topics that have been discussed in this research; they were: talking about self (I am a nurse), Congratulating and Complimenting Others (Congratulating and Complimenting Patient), and Expressing Intention (Patient Care).

In addition, based on the finding in the part of the interview to the teacher and some of the x grade student in nursing vocational, it was found that the students do not have a useful skill in English especially in speaking. Mostly, they have a willingness to speak and practice English, but they are not confident because they have lack of vocabularies and afraid of making a mistake in pronouncing the English words related to their major. Besides, the content of the questionnaire related to the student's need. The questionnaire proposed by some expert; Lamb (1996, p 34-8) in Wello and Doliah (2008, p.79) theory related to the students' background (name, age, experience in learning English, the duration of using English and students' proficiency level in English), Hutchinson and Waters (1987) theory related to the target needs (goals, necessities, lacks and wants). Then, Nunan (2004) theory related to the learning needs (input, procedures, setting, teachers' role and learners' role). But, the parts of the questionnaire transform based on nursing vocational.

After the researcher finding the students need, the researcher starts to analyze the questionnaire and find out the English speaking materials related to the nursing vocational and link the material appropriate with the 2013 curriculum. Then, the researcher applied 3 kinds of English speaking materials for nursing vocational; they are; I am a nurse, congratulating and complimenting others, and patient care. The researcher only develops 3 units because in this parts of the main point of the students do in their workplace.

In unit 1 until unit 3, this related to the topic talking about self, congratulating and complimenting others and expressing intention in the students' book 2013 curriculum. The researcher is researching the place of their workplace to find out what the first step they do in the hospital or clinic. Moreover, the researcher found that, before the patient going to say what are the reasons they come to the hospital or the clinic, the nurse starts to greeting the patient and introduce their self. After that nurse taking patient's data included their name, age, marital status, occupation, health insurance (asks, BPJS or others), and so on. Congratulate and compliment the patient and patient care to make the patient comfortable in doing the medication.

Therefore, the researcher put role-play, pair works, and discussion and make a short dialog then practice in front of the classroom. The reason uses role play, pair works and discussion related to their need in the questionnaire. Then, the main reason the researcher asked them to make a short dialog is to enhance the students' motivation and confidence in speaking English.

Additionally, in developing the English speaking materials, the researcher link it with the standard competence, basic competence, indicators and aim of learning. The basic competence based on SK Dirjen Dikbudmen No.330 /D.D5/Kep/KR/2017. It is important for the teacher and the students to have this English speaking materials or nursing vocational because in the XII grade nursing vocational students will practice in the hospital and clinic in Gorontalo except for Toto hospital in three months. This is the best way for the students as their preparation before they are going to continue their study as a nurse. Also, there are some medical journals mostly using English. The result of the data showed that English speaking materials could make the student's vocabularies, grammar and pronunciation increase. It was supported by the experts that they agreed that English speaking materials for nursing vocational could encourage students speaking skill and their motivation in speaking English. The student very enthusiasm to practice English in front of the classroom related to their vocational. Mostly, they want to practice English by bringing the nurse practice tools such as a stethoscope, medicine, injection and doll (when they want to practice as a midwife). As a conclusion, applying English speaking materials for nursing vocational gives a lot of opportunities to speak English and gives advantages to the students of nursing vocational at X grade.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

5.1 Conclusion

There are four conclusions in this research, the conclusion about the students' responded background, the target needs of X grade students in SMK N 1 Bulango Selatan, the learning needs of X grade students in SMK N 1 Bulango Selatan and the characteristics of the appropriate supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational school of X grade students in SMK N 1 Bulango Selatan.

5.1.2 Students' Responded Background

Before researching the target needs and learning needs of the students, it is necessary to know first about the student's knowledge and experience in learning English. It was found that the students have a lack experience in learning English especially in speaking. Mostly, the students admit that their English proficiency level is average, and others are bad.

5.1.3 Target Needs

The things that the students needed to do in the target situation where the target needs. There were forth terms in the target needs. They were the goal, necessities lacks and

wants in learning speaking. The goal was for the students needed to wanted to have a good grade in learning English and can pass the examination. The other option was the students needed to be able to support their career in the field of nursing. The necessities was the students use English but unable to respond. For the lacks, the students still found difficulties in discussing either in groups or in pairs in speaking. The last for wants, the students wished to be able to communicating by using grammar correctly, to communicate in English fluently, and mastering English vocabulary related to the field of or department in nursing.

5.1.4 Learning Needs

The learning needs were about the students' opinions about what they should do to achieve the target situation. There were fifth terms in learning needs, setting, input, procedures, learners' role and teachers' role. Based on the research, it was found that in the students needed to learn in pairs or group in the type of class management the students want in doing the task. Moreover, the students needed 50-150 words in the length of the text in speaking English material. They also want monologue and dialogue accompanied by a list of vocabulary and pronunciation for the input in speaking English materials. In addition, for the activities of vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and speaking, they wanted to match words with images, complete the utterance/dialogue by using the correct grammar, repeat the teacher's words that are considered difficult, and role play or discussion. In the learners' role, the students liked to listen to the teacher's explanation well. Last, they were expecting teachers to provide examples of assignments given to students and helping them if there are students who have problems.

5.1.5 Developing Supplementary English Speaking Materials for Nursing Vocational

In developing the materials, the researcher used theory from Borg and Gall (1983). There are 10 steps; 1) research and information collecting, 2) Planning, 3) Develop Preliminary Form of Product, 4) Preliminary Field Testing, 5) Main Product Revision, 6) Main Field Testing, 7) Operational Product Revision, 8) Operational Product Field Testing, 9) Final Product Revision and 10) Dissemination/Implementation. But, the researcher only used six steps, they are: 1) research and information collecting, 2) Planning, 3) Develop Preliminary Form of Product, 4) Preliminary Field Testing, 5) Main Product Revision, 6) Main Field Testing.

The developing supplementary English speaking materials for nursing vocational school product for X grade students in nursing vocational has been developed, evaluated, revised and tried out in the classroom. The result was the students very motivated in learning speaking English; they are active in teaching and learning process because they never practice speaking English related their major. The teachers are supported and very grateful because supplementary English speaking materials can reduce the student's problem especially in speaking English. It can be seen from the teachers' expectation to have this product in their school.

5.2 Suggestions

5.2.1 English Teachers

This supplementary English speaking materials book for nursing vocational can be used as the materials to teach the students in the teaching and learning process especially in speaking. This book aimed to improve and enhance the students' speaking skill. Teachers can use supplementary English speaking materials book to teach some expressions in English used in the field of nursing.

5.2.2 Other Researchers

The supplementary English speaking materials book for nursing vocational was developed for X grade. It consisted of various interesting activities based on their needs in need analysis. Moreover, other researchers are expected could make more interesting, innovative and useful learning materials with different theme, activities, in teaching speaking related to the nursing vocational. By conducting the needs analysis, other researchers are expected to know the needs and interests of the students in order to make it relevant.

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